

TEACHERS' AND COMMUNICATION: EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF TEACHERS' EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN PRESENT-DAY CLASSROOM ENVIRONMENTS – A SYSTEMATIC ANALYSIS FROM LITERATURE

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Article Info

Keywords: Communication, Communication skills, Digitalized classroom, Teachers, Digital environments.

DOI

10.5281/zenodo.18373479

Abstract

Human beings are communal, involved in social interactions and drawn to each other and perform their different functions on daily basis based on certain competences. They are usually involved in one form of communication or the other, and the purpose of such interactions is for clear and effective communication. For effective interactions to take place, they must understand or recognize the body language cues and develop effective listening skills, which may be essential tools for job and also builds good social relationships. In today's classroom therefore, teachers' effective communication is pivotal, especially in modern digitalization of education, which impacts students learning and motivation. They need robust communication skills to navigate digital tools, foster student engagement, and create inclusive learning spaces, both in-person and online engagements. This paper concisely discussed the effective and skillful ways teachers/educators communicate with students/learners to enable them comprehend effectively within and outside the classroom settings without ambiguity. It examined the impact of teachers' effective and poor communication skills in teaching-learning classroom environments. Additionally, the paper likewise probed the obstacles inherent in teachers' effective communication skills, especially in the modern digitalized education system, and expressly in Nigerian context. The authors proffer solutions to the identified challenges.

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Introduction

Communication is fundamental in human life. This statement has been affirmed by Zlatovic (2018). The scholar opined that communication with others is an essential part of every aspect of our entire life experience, our development, our personal lives, and in education. In teaching and learning, effective communication has been acclaimed to be the cornerstone for teacher's successful teaching that fosters a strong and dynamic learning environment, where students feel understood, respected, and motivated. Sword (2020) affirmed that communication is key in the classroom, and asserts that successful teaching is generally considered to require only 50% knowledge to 50% communication skills. Be that as it may, a teacher should be proficient enough in all four modes of communication that is, listening, speaking, reading, and writing. At the same time should also know how to utilize this proficiency effectively in a school environment. The effective use of these communication modes has been proven to improve students' success and achieve in their academic lives, as well as the teacher's own career success Sword (2020). Does not only involve verbal interactions (talking) to people, but also involves non-verbal communication. Communication is not really an easy process because it is full of certain difficulties due to individual differences and perceptions. This has been affirmed by some statements, such as, I don't understand what you are saying; "You don't seem to have understood me"; I don't really mean that"; "You don't seem to grasped the point"; etc. (Stanton, 2004).

However, communication is both a medium and an essential aim of modern and globalized education system, which requires people, especially teachers to think critically and communicate effectively to solve problems and develop collaborations in many ways under difficult and various circumstances (Reimers & Chung, 2016). Communication affects teaching-learning process. In one way, teaching is communication; hence, it is essential for a teacher to build good and effective communication skills, which is very essential to the transfer of knowledge, which involves talking or other forms of communication, listening and accepting information (Zlatovic, 2018).

We communicate for several purposes, such as to inform, explain, persuade, entertain, convince, educate, etc. Nonetheless, the four main objectives of communication as Stanton (2004) put it are: (1). to be received (to be heard); (2). to be understood; (3). to be accepted; (4). to get action (change of behaviour or attitude). According to this scholar, once we fail to accomplish any of these, we have failed in communication, and this may lead to serious frustration and resentment (anger, bitterness or offence). As a teacher, educator, or a parent that used to help children with their homework, the skillful way or the manner you present your ideas or course materials to them matters a lot to their understanding. They are the ones we teach; hence, we must use a simple, correct and moderate communication skills to pass our experiences to them.

In the school environment, communication is very important because a teacher who cannot effectively commutate to his students will not meaningfully transmit any good thought or experience to his students. This paper will concisely discuss the effective and skillful ways by which the teachers/educators could communicate with students/learners to enable them comprehend effectively within and outside the classroom environments/settings without ambiguity. It will also examine the impact of teachers' effective and poor communication skills in teaching and learning classroom environments. Additionally, the paper will likewise probe the obstacles or challenges inherent in teachers' effective communication skills, especially in the modern digitalized education system, and expressly in Nigerian context. The authors will also proffer solutions to the identified challenges as identified.

Review of Related Literature

Generally, all living creatures need to communicate; it is the driving force in any relationship, and a continuous process of sending and receiving messages, which enhances the dissemination of knowledge, attitudes, and skills. Communication is a personal, social, and a psychosocial process that builds relationship between two individuals. People need to exchange ideas in their daily activities in order to survive and solve their various problems; it may include both verbal and non-verbal communication methods. In the education sector, communication is inevitable and teachers' ability to convey their thoughts, experiences or ideas, depends on their communication effectiveness to deliver their messages across to their students. According to Akhigbe (2025) communication is central and indispensable in the classroom teaching and learning process, and it is a very important component of the teaching and learning, without which it would be impossible to teach or learn.

However, for effective grasp of the subject matter, let's give meanings to most of the terms and phrases.

Definition/Meaning of Terms

Communication: Communication is the act of giving information or message from one person to another. It is a way of making one's ideas, concept, principles and information clear or explicit to others (Ajileye, 2016). Communication skills have also been explained as involving listening, speaking, reading and writing (Freddie, n.d.). Communication occurs when two or more persons' exchange information and send and receive different data to achieve a specific and clear goal (Rise vision 2023). Communication means the process which one adopts while sharing his / her views with others Khan, Khan, Zia-Ul-Islam and Khan (2017). In the education sector, the teachers communicate information to students while the student's receiver that information.

Digitalized Classroom: This refers to an educational environment where technology and digital tools are integrated to enhance teaching and learning. This includes using electronic devices (computer, smartboards, telephone, and other digital resources) to deliver content, facilitate interaction, and support students' learning. Digital classrooms can encompass various approaches, such as computer-based learning, web-based learning, and virtual classrooms (<https://www.google.com/search?q=What+is+Digitalized+Classroom>). It may also be a technology-integrated learning environment, which uses devices, such as tablet, laptops, and software like the Learning Management System, and the internet to enhance teaching. Additionally, it also incorporates digital tools like online resources, smart boards, and real-time feedback for dynamic learning, offering interactive, collaborative, and personalized education (https://www.google.com/search?q=Define%3Adigital+classroom&sca_esv=36c52ed8992032f9&source=hp&ei=

Classroom Environments: Refers to a conducive and spacious or sizeable classroom that includes facilities like light, enough ventilation, adequate physical facilities and materials, and well-arranged isolated but free from distractions, where teaching-learning takes place.

Teacher: A teacher is an individual, typically a professional teacher, who provides training or instruction, guides students in acquiring knowledge, skills, and values, and nurtures their academic and social-emotional growth. A teacher, also called an educator, helps students to acquire information or knowledge, skills and virtue. A teacher is a person who facilitates learning by imparting knowledge, skills, and values to students. He creates an engaging learning experiences for students/learners; he develops lesson plans, assesses students' general progress, and also acts as a facilitator and mentor to help them succeed and become active members of any given society. In totality, the teacher they inspire, motivate, and guide students on their educational journeys. (<https://www.google.com/search?q=define%3ATeacher&oq=define%3ATeacher>).

Digitalized Environment: A digital environment refers to the increasing integration of digital technologies into various aspects of life, which is transforming the way we interact, work, and conduct business. It is a virtual or computer-generated space created by technology where users interrelate through digital interfaces and devices, rather than physical face-to-face. It encompasses everything from the software and hardware that enable these effective interactions, such as computers, phones, and networks, to the content, information, and activities within them, such as websites, apps, virtual worlds, and online collaboration platforms. These environments are used for work, learning, entertainment, and social connection, fundamentally altering how people communicate, conduct transactions, and experience reality. (<https://www.google.com/search?q=Define%3ADigitalized+Environment&oq=>).

Concept of Communication in Teaching-Learning Process

Effective communication in education by teachers help create a conducive learning environment and improves student understanding and learning outcomes. Khan, Khan, Zia-Ul-Islam and Khan (2017) revealed that good communication skills of teachers are the basic need of academic success of students, and professional success of life. Teachers can create a more orderly and productive environment in teaching-learning environment if they significantly apply effective communication skills and employing strategies that foster clear expectations, consistent consequences, and positive reinforcement classroom management. In support of the above assertion, the results of the regression test by Tariq & Ullah (2024) showed a positive but insignificant impact of teachers' communication skills on the academic achievement of students at the secondary school level.

Teachers communicate more instructions orally in classroom to students and they totally depend on the communication skills of teachers for effective understanding, and teachers with poor communication skills may cause students failure and promote academic outcome Khan, Khan, Zia-Ul-Islam and Khan (2017). Teachers who apply good communication strategies can achieve educational goals more effectively (Mahdi 2023). There are different methods of communication that are available for teachers in teaching-learning process. Let's examine the meaning of communication in teaching-learning process. Communication originated from a Latin word "Communis", which undoubtedly means "to share" (Uche, Awujo and Agbakwuru, 2014).

Through communication, we can express ourselves in various ways. Communication has been conceptualized as the exchange of thoughts, message or information through speeches, visual, writing or signal. It involves the exchange of information between individuals, which is achieve through the following means, such as signs, symbols, or behaviours in an attempt to understand each other (Uche, Awujo and Agbakwuru, 2014). In teaching-learning process, conclusively, communication is the transmission of or the process of conveying information, idea, facts and knowledge from the teacher to the learners (Ajilewye, 2016).

Classifying Communication

Communication could be classified into 4 types, such as (1) Verbal (2) Non-verbal (3) Interpersonal, and (4) Intrapersonal. Each of these play a very vital role in information sharing among humans. The above methods of communication have lots of implications for students and teachers and could be expatiated below thus:

Verbal Communication: Verbal communication is the spoken word that all of us are involved on daily basis. It involves the use of sound (spoken words) and language; taking to someone (student/learner) face-to-face interaction or through the microphone, or any other technology devices that contains sound. Spoken works or talking is used to clarify ideas, inform, persuade people, inquire, argue or discuss various issues that border on human existence/activities (Damiella, 2010).

Non-Verbal Communication: Non-verbal communication does not require the use of spoken words. It involves the use of body language, such as signs and symbols, facial expressions, postures and body orientations, eye contact, silence, etcetera.

Interpersonal Communication: In this form of communication, two or more persons are usually involved. Interpersonal Communication involves both verbal and non-verbal in exchange of thoughts, experiences, or knowledge. It is one-on-one or face-to-face dialogue or interaction that aim to exchange ideas. Uche, Awujo, and Agbakwuru (2014) stated that the elements of inter-personal communication include the communicators, the message, the noise, the feedback, and the context and the channel.

Intrapersonal Communication: Intrapersonal communication is purely private and happens within a person's mind. It does not require a second party. The individual assumes the role of a sender and at the same time the receiver. However, it has been defined by Roberts, Edwards and Barker in Burnette-Lernon (2012) as all the physiological and psychological processing of messages that happens within the individuals at conscious and non-conscious levels as they attempt to understand themselves and their environment. This, as the scholars' stated include perceptions, ideas, thoughts, feelings that happens within oneself. Good examples of it are – soliloquizing (talking to oneself), day-dreaming. The above types of communication could be used to convey knowledge to the students in the classroom.

Need for Teachers' Effective Communication in Teaching-Learning Environment

The rapid development of advance technology has transformed and changed the communication landscape around the world. We are today in a world where communication is no longer limited to face-to-face interactions, but extended to various digital platforms and communication technologies. Effective communication between the teachers and the students has the potential to improve the learning experiences and create a positive classroom environment. Firstly, what makes teachers communication effective in the classroom environments? What are the possible reasons why communication is termed to be effective between teachers and students/learners in modern-day classroom environments?

Effective communication between the teachers and the students has the potential to improve the learning experiences and create a positive classroom environment. Firstly, what makes teachers communication effective in the classroom environments? What are the possible reasons why communication is termed to be effective between teachers and students/learners in a modern-day classroom environment?

In the field of education however, communication plays a very pivotal role in the teaching-learning process, as communication is no longer unidirectional and less interactive, where teachers dominate the teaching-learning actions, and the students often passive in the classroom. This process has led to inequality in the teaching-learning and presents a negative effect on student learning outcomes (Jandevi, 2019). Now, let's examine how good and effective communication skills by the teachers or educators that could appropriately pass their information or learning content to the students/learners in the classroom setting.

Teaching and learning require good and effective communication skills that are most vital for interactions with students, because they are responsible for comprehending and breaking down complex information into bits, and convey such information clearly, verbally, and in written format to students in a manner that sustains their attention, and listening to them and resolving their questions or problems amicably through a good feedback mechanism.

Teachers' communication skills and teaching effectiveness in the classroom environment is very sacrosanct in both online and offline environments; the teacher needs to make his communication very simple and short, and straight to the point to avoid ambiguity. For communication to be effective for both the sender and the receiver

in this type of classroom situation, there must be clear explanations of ideas or concepts. The teacher as the sender must clearly explain certain issues or concepts to the understanding of the receiver. In the same process, the students, who is the receiver of the information from the teacher must as well listen attentively to understand and grasp the main idea that the teacher passes to them. If the students do not listen attentively, no matter how eloquent and effective the teacher communicates, communication will hardly take place.

Again, in a two-way communication, one party will definitely listen to the other in a communication process. Hence, in a teaching-learning situation, while the students listen to the teacher, the teacher should also listen to the student to hear from him. For instance, where the student is not quite clear of what the teacher said, the student should be able to clarify some issues for a better understanding. In this way, the teacher will explain more and there will be a better understanding of the ideas and communication will flow adequately.

Effective communication demands that as Mr. A listens to Mr. B's ideas, Mr. B should as well listen to Mr. A's idea. It is when individuals start clarifying these ideas that they will understand themselves better. This is more pronounced when people are working as group. In this case, no idea is more superior to the other in a group. The teachers, the parents, and the guardians should have this at the back of their minds that children or students sometimes possess noble ideas that may be very important in a discussion. Teachers have to listen to students' ideas and accept whichever one that is good or meaningful. Therefore, it is very important for teachers to give listening ears to students in a group discussion or project to get good ideas and acknowledge where possible.

Furthermore, immediate feedback is very important, especially in any online interaction. In the classroom situation, the teacher cannot know if the message he sends to the students is understood by the student unless he gets reliable feedback denoting that the information passed to them is understood. Feedback enables two persons in a communication process to know if communication has really taken place the way it is intended.

To keep communication flowing between two persons in a communication process, some of the body languages must come to play, especially the eye contact, which enables individuals in the communication process to remain focused to one another. In as much as sound (talking) plays important role in the communication process, non-verbal methods of communication also play a vital role in enhancing understanding among individuals.

A teacher's good communication skills are important requirement necessary to pilot students'/learners' academic activities in the classroom. It will not be an overstatement to say that effective communication benefits everyone, because effective communication influences the interest and attitude of the students in creating a fun and learning atmosphere; it also helps to improve relationships, increase understanding, and model positive interactions among individuals in a given society. Sword (2020) avowed that teaching requires effective communication to interact positively with students/learners, parents and colleagues. It has been affirmed that effective teaching-learning process cannot take place if the teachers cannot effectively communicate to his students in the classroom. Sword (2020) further stated that poor communication skill and poor teaching methods causes students' comprehension levels to drop, and may affect their academic progress negatively. Consequently, teachers with good and effective communication skills creates a more successful teaching and learning atmosphere for the students. Therefore, students' success in learning situation is greatly influenced by the teachers' effective communication skills.

Tariq and Ulla (2024) in one of their research findings observed the impact of teachers' communication skills on the academic achievement of students at the secondary school level. The scholars noted that teachers use speaking and writing skills better than listening and body language skills, and the impact of teachers' communication skills on the academic achievement of students was positive but low and insignificant. In

contrary to Tariq and Ulla (2024), Sword (2020), affirmed that communication is key in the classroom. The scholar confirmed that communication has been proven to impact the success students achieve in their academic lives, as well as the teacher's own career success. The author observed that successful teaching generally requires only 50% knowledge and 50% communication skills. For communication to be effective in the classroom, the scholar recommends that the teacher should be proficient in all the four modes of communication, which are - listening, speaking, reading, and writing, and should also know how to utilize them proficiently and effectively in a school environment.

Sword (2020) stressed that both in verbally and in written format, that communication skills are most vital for interactions with students because it is one of the requirements for the act of teaching, which the teacher will use to adapt content for different learning styles, motivate students to learn, build supportive relationships using encouragement and empathy, manage the classroom, and give feedback, comprehend and break-down complex information, conveying this information clearly to students, and presenting it in a way that sustains their attention, and listening, and also resolving their questions or problems, thereby making your classroom a safe and supportive learning environment.

As part of teacher's communication methods, which may be both verbal and written language, he will also need to communicate effectively with parents. This might be through a veracity of methods, such as phone calls, emails, and one-on-one interactions to discuss important subjects, such as students behaviour issues, learning problems, such as revealing their children's academic strengths and weaknesses in school. Inability of any teacher to interact well, clearly, and tactful to parents always could lead to doubts on their part about his ability to convey his ideas or experiences to the students they teach.

Again, as part of the commutation processes, good teaching does not require independent but collaborative work, which may be planning lessons together, updating colleagues on certain students' progress, staff meetings, training sessions, give feedback to other staff, exchange of ideas on how to handle some problems in the classroom. Consequently, effective communication skills will be of essence. As we have demonstrated, there are many reasons why effective communication skills are imperative in a teaching career.

Kumar and Rekha (2021) affirmed that teachers' effective use of the skills below while communication in classroom environment would result to positive learning outcomes. They are: -

- The knowledge of the teacher about the content and subject matter

- Language used by the teacher during interaction
- Teachers teaching methodology
- Teaching-learning materials used during the teaching learning process
- Physical & social environment of the classroom
- Timing
- Teachers' communication skills (gestures/ body language, etc.)
- Relation between teachers & students.
- The use of technology, etcetera.

The above list shows that the effectiveness of teachers' communication skills is directly dependent or determines the success of students in the classroom. Therefore, for teachers to be productive in the classroom, good communication skills are needed for a better positive interaction with the learners/students, which will undoubtedly lead to a successful academic outcome. Kumar and Rekha (2021) have added yet another important information on effective communication in the classroom. The scholars revealed that effective

communications serve both functional and psychological purposes. Functional purpose satisfies and tries to fulfill the aims and objectives of teaching-learning process in the classroom, while psychological purpose enhances the interpersonal skills and interaction of each and every student in the classroom. The scholars reminded us that the teachers in the learning processes should now the amount of knowledge and skills, experiences, attitudes, aptitudes, competences in language, etc. and the student possess.

However, Kumar and Rekha (2021) affirmed that four type of communication are mainly used by teachers in classroom communication. The scholars revealed the teachers' knowledge and their mastery over communication skills are helpful for the educational & behavioral development of students as well as teacher's development.

Summarily, effective communication skills can help teachers increase learning effectiveness, ensure better understanding by students, and better achieve learning goals. Teachers effective communication skills in the classroom play an important role in education as outlined hereunder by Mahdi (2023) thus: -

1. helps teachers convey information clearly and students understand course material;
2. motivates students to learn and relates the subject matter to their daily lives;
3. helps students develop social skills, such as public speaking and collaborating with peers;
4. allows students participate in discussions and find solutions together to solve problems;
5. used to teach values, such as hard work, discipline, tolerance, and empathy;
6. involves giving feedback to students about their performance, as well as receiving feedback from students about their learning, and
7. helps create a conducive learning environment and improves student understanding and learning outcomes. help achieve educational goals more effectively.

Generally, more possible reasons have also been giving for what constitute effective communication between the teachers and the students/learners alike.

- he must be vast in both verbal and non-verbal communication skills to take a good control of the classroom setting, and for the students/learners to better comprehend the objectives of the lesson. Communication does not only involve talking, which involves the use of sound, but also involves other non-verbal communication, which their existence cannot be ignored. The teachers/educators must be vast in the effective use of both verbal and non-verbal communication skills to actively interact with students and pass the required wealth of experiences adequately without any form of misconceptions or ambiguity. The teachers need to communicate effectively to pass their ideas, issues, concepts, rules, processes, and skills to their students\learners.

- Kumar and Rekha (2021) affirmed that effective communication is considered a strong and essential tool for effectiveness in the teaching learning process. The scholars stressed that a teacher may be very knowledgeable in his field, but if he cannot convey or transfer such in a way it is intended to, then, it will not serve the purpose. In this case, the lesson is as good as not being presented to students/learners at all. It is important for the teachers to clearly articulate their thoughts and ideas orally or in written format for the students/learners, which if poorly communicated will be very disastrous to the students'/learners' academic achievements. Oftentimes, students' poor performance in class activities may be attributed to teachers' lack of adequate communication skills. It is on record that some teachers possess enough knowledge in their fields, but lack adequate communication skills to successfully pass the knowledge to their students/learners.

• Another effective method of communicating to students is to move and walk around in the classroom environment. Zlatovic (2018) put it thus: “It’s been proven that educators who walk around and talk, and not just sit and read from the text, get better feedback from students; the best option is to combine dynamic, non-verbal presentation with expressive speech patterns, using repetition and emphasis in one’s voice to make important concepts stand out”. Positive feedback informs the teacher if he is doing a good job in the classroom. This feedback may come from the student if the teacher is sure he understood the lesson, or someone from outside, who the teacher positioned to monitor his presentation in the classroom.

Akhigbe (2025) emphasized that the main purpose of classroom communication is to educate students/learners; through effective communication skills, teachers could pass their information or instruction to the learners, which help to educate, inform and transform the learned. The author declared that classroom communication is mainly on the message and feedback. For effective communication to take place, Kumar (2021) and Everstudy Classes (2025) affirmed that teachers must observe and focus on the undermentioned factors to interact positively with students/learners, and for the teaching and learning to be successful; the success will depend directly and effectively on good communication skills; without, the teacher cannot interact positively with students (Akhigbe, 2025). The factors are: -

(1. Content of the subject matter (2). The goal of the communication should be clearly and specifically stated (3). Receiving reactions and a response from the receiver or learners (4). Instilling the motives of the content for all parties to understand. (5). The knowledge of the teacher about the content and subject matter (6). Language used by the teacher during interaction (7). Teachers teaching methodology and style (8). Teaching learning material and teaching aids (9). Physical and social environment of the class room (10). Teachers’ communication skills (gestures/ body language etc.). (11). Teacher and students’ relationship. (12). The use of technologies.

When teachers observe the factors above it means that teaching and learning will be successful and the success will depend directly on communication skills, without having a good communication the teacher cannot interact positively with students (Akhigbe, 2025)

Kumar (2021), in his research work, stressed that “The communication could be more effective when the teacher lays proper stress on various points: • Appropriate planning • Clarity of message • Completeness of message • Language of message • Appropriate vocabulary • Selection of ways of communication • Relevant and detailed statements • Continuity of the communication • Timing • Use of effective, meaningful and interesting illustration with examples • Formulation of simple, interesting and relevant examples & teaching aids • Effective Facial expression (Eye contact, body posture etc.) • Stress on words • Modulation of voice • Effective use of stimulus variation • Clarity about medium • Use of appropriate media for communication • Listening • Give & receive feedback”.

Consequences of Teachers’ Ineffective Communication Skills in Teaching-Learning process

There is nothing more that significantly hinders and creates a negative learning environment for students/learners than ineffective communication skills in the classroom by the teachers. Teachers poor communication skills reduce students' comprehension levels in the classroom, which may negatively reduce or affect their academic progress (<https://www.toppr.com/bytes/failure-communication-between-teachers-and-students/>). This process can make them become more confused, disengaged, and develop negative attitudes towards learning. However, teachers’ ineffective communication skills do not only involve verbal or face-to-face communication skills, but also involve written and non-verbal aspects of communication. Then, what are

the possible reasons why communication fails between teachers and students/learners in modern-day classroom environment? In answer to the above question, Kumar and Rekha (2021) have observed and listed some of the weakness found in teachers' ineffective communication skills in the classroom.

Verbal Communication Skill: On verbal communication skill, which impedes learning among students/learners during teaching-learning process, such as: -

- (1). Poor command on the subject
- (2). Use of monotonous voice
- (3). Badly expressed message
- (4). Not establish eye to eye contact
- (5). Lack of logical and psychological sequence during teaching-learning process
- (6). Difference in language used by the teacher & student
- (7) Providing too many facts without linking them properly
- (8). Message overloading
- (9). Wrong timing
- (10). Noise in the environment
- (11). Use of ambiguous words
- (12). Poorly chosen words
- (13) Poor organization of ideas
- (14). Inadequate verbal communication
- (15). Lack of listening and speaking skill.

Non-verbal Communication Skills: Another one is non-verbal communication skills that impede students' learning. They are: - (i). Uncoordinated movements & timing (ii). Hand & head movements (iii). Sounds and smile (iv). Closeness (v). Posture, etc. It may also lead to student's lack of motivation, disliking school and even the teacher, and may make them not to believe in themselves as they find it difficult to achieve their desired goals. Teachers communication barriers in the classroom certainly makes it difficult for students to comprehend, and fails to create engaging lessons. In this case, the teachers struggle to connect with their students on a one-to-one basis (<https://www.toppr.com/bytes/failure-communication-between-teachers-and-students/>).

On the other hand, it has also been noticed that poor communication skills in the classroom does not only depend on the teachers alone, but students also have their own communication challenges. Their unaddressed language or speech difficulties also leads to poor communication in the classroom. Personality differences and peer pressure add to the mix, making some classroom interactions feel awkward or difficult (<https://www.toppr.com/bytes/failure-communication-between-teachers-and-students/>).

Summarily, Kumar and Rekha (2021) opined that research shows that teachers' ineffective communication skills in the classroom would result to the following undermentioned consequences to students: -

- (i). Low interaction
- (ii). Student's poor performance
- (iii). Boring classroom teaching-learning process
- (iv). Unable to understand or comprehend
- (v). Improve in the rote memory
- (vi). Increase in dropout rates
- (vii). Let down the respect of teachers
- (viii). Not able to learn & implement communication skills
- (ix). Lack of confidence among the students
- (x). Low achievement in academic performance.

Written Communication: Written communication can affect teacher's communication in the classroom in several ways. The following were observed as factors that impede learning in the classroom setting:

(i). Late or Delayed Feedback: This happens when students couldn't easily read the teachers notes, thereby does not immediate clarify issues. In such a situation, the students will misunderstand the content and could not ask immediate questions arising from the written material.

(ii). Time Consuming: It is imperative that if teachers did not balance written communication with oral discussions and demonstrations for effective time management in the classroom, they will consume a lot of time. The time consuming arises from the time spent preparing written materials, slow transmission from the written materials to students, time used in reading and interpreting the written document. Others are extra time spent for explanation of the written materials, time spent marking assignments, the feedback time, rewriting and correction of unclear notes, and correcting spelling, grammar, and by adjusting poorly written instructions on the board.

(iii). Lack of expression & inefficiency: When lack of inefficiency is noticed on the side of the teacher's communication in the classroom situation, this reduces the effectiveness of the lesson, particularly when explanation takes a longer time, lesson not completed in due time, the time meant for practical is lost mostly to discussions, etc.

(iv). Lack of flexibility: If a teacher is unable to communicate effectively his ideas or thought clearly and effectively to the students in the classroom, this will negatively affect his output and affect students' learning outcome in the following ways. The teacher may not clearly deliver his lesson appropriate to his student/pupils as this may lead to poorly organized explanations that will confuse the students, and they will also misunderstand the teacher. The teacher will not be able to manage his time very well as most of the time will be used explaining a simple idea and miss the key leaning points. Also, students will find it extremely to understand the task at hand and become frustrated, which normally will lower or slow down the learning process.

Visual communication: This method of communication has also been an impediment to poor classroom communication. Poorly designed visual aids or wrong images distract and impede the understanding of concepts. If teachers should make sure that their visuals are well designed, very clear, and can be visible to students/learners in the classroom, irrespective of their positions, they will effectively communicate their ideas and thoughts to students with ease.

Intrapersonal Communication: Intrapersonal communication, which is private communication within oneself in nature also impede communication, especially among the students/learners. When a student/learner has physiological and/or psychological problems, it will be very difficult for them to concentrate on the teacher's lesson in the classroom. A student that is hungry, lost a parent, or a close relation may not be concerned on what the teacher is teaching. The student/learner may be soliloquizing or day-dreaming in the classroom when the teacher is interacting with the class.

Suggestions for Teachers' Effective Communication in Classroom Environment

Effective communication in the classroom involves the teachers and the students/learners alike. When each of these bodies adopt the under-listed measures, effective communication will definitely be established or take place. It is very important for teachers to communicate clearly, confidently and effectively in the classroom to easily or straightforwardly deliver the content to students.

Short Sentences: Teachers should avoid the use of long sentences while delivering their lessons. The use of short words and short sentences go well with young learners, thereby making possible for them to avoid confusion. This makes communication go straight to the points.

Listening and understanding: There is no doubt that one of the most important aspects of effective communication in the classroom is listening and understanding of the message. Effective communication requires active listening and understanding by the students in the classroom. No matter the modes of communication used by the teacher, active and effective listening and understanding is pivotal to understanding what the teacher is communicating. In the same way, unless the teacher understands clearly what the student is telling him, the teacher cannot respond appropriately to what the students/learners actually required. Sward (2020) opined that a teacher should be proficient in all four modes of communication – listening, speaking, reading, and writing - and should know how to utilize them proficiently and effectively in a school environment.

Listen attentively: A good teacher must listen attentively and effectively to his students to understand their problems and solve them appropriately.

Use of Clear and Simple Words: Today, spoken words are mostly used to communicate ideas, thoughts, or experiences to students/learners in the classroom environment. Teachers are advised to make use of very simple or modest words that suit the level of the students thought. Big or difficult words should be explained or defined to bring the message home to the students. These words will easily convey the right meaning to their audience. They should avoid using ambiguous words that are usually prone to different interpretations, and that will easily confuse the students/learners. So, using the right words to the right audience will definitely make a difference. Clarity of the message used by the teachers will improve the understanding of the students.

Effective Facial expression: The effective use of eye contact and body gesture will improve teachers communication skills in the classroom.

Use the Right Language: Teachers should use the language the student/learners will understand. When teachers use the language that is foreign to students/learners, it will be very difficult for them to comprehend what is thought.

Speak to be Heard: Some teachers hardly speak what the whole students will hear. Thereby making it very difficult for them to hear and understand. Therefore, teachers should speak to the hearing of the students/learners to comprehend the message.

Use of Illustration: Teachers' use of effective, meaningful and interesting illustrations with examples will help to improve the understanding of the students. Proper formulation of simple, interesting, and relevant teaching instructional media will enhance the

Don't Speak Too Fast or Too slow: The teacher must know the level and capabilities of the students. Therefore, the teacher has to speak to the level of the students he teaches. He should speak moderately, and not too fast or too slow. Naturally, some persons are not gifted to understand persons when they speak too fast or slow. Any of these will impede learning.

Use Friendly Voice or Tone: Unfriendly voice distracts the students in the classroom. Unfriendly voice of tone will portray the teacher as a harsh person and the students will be afraid of you. Using a friendly voice will radiate love among the students. Unfriendly voice or tone may even make some students, who did not grow in a harsh environment to stay away from the class.

Teaching Environment: The teaching environment has a lot to play in teaching and learning process. Firstly, it plays a significant role on how he shapes his thoughts and communicates same to the betterment and the understanding of the students in the classroom. Good classroom arrangement, could enable the teacher see the students' facial expressions clearly, and also enable the students' to see the teacher's sign languages clearly.

Make Lesson Interesting: The teachers should make teaching interesting for the students/pupils. This method would reduce day-dreaming among students/pupils in the classroom. Some teachers are student friendly, while some are hard on the students through shouting or bullying, and frowning their faces while teaching. Additionally, some teachers will ask questions and if the student did not get the question rightly, they abuse to the student, and sometimes extend it to their parents and guardians. This keeps the students off or away from class most of the times.

Summary

The authors of this paper have articulated most of what they expressed to discuss by given a systematic analysis from literature the impact of teachers' effective and ineffective communication skills in the present-day classroom environments, nothing that the teachers' effective communication is pivotal to the present-day teaching-learning process, especially in this period of digitalization of education, which impacts more on students learning and motivation. The authors were able to concisely conceptualize communication, the

classification, and the need for teachers' effective communication skills in teaching-learning environment. They also briefed us on the consequences of teachers' ineffective communication skills in modern classroom and equally made effective suggestions for teachers' effective communication skills. Finally, appropriate conclusion and recommendations were made to improve teachers' effective communication skills for the betterment of students learning outcome.

Conclusion

Teaching-learning is not an easy task. To learn is to acquire knowledge or experiences, while to teach involves giving somebody (learners') instruction to know how to do something. It has been affirmed that effective teaching and learning processes cannot take place if the teachers cannot effectively and skillfully communicate their ideas or thoughts to students in the classroom. Teachers' effective communication skills can improve or make students' learning progress in the classroom. Therefore, students' success or failure in teaching and learning situations is greatly influenced by teachers' effective and ineffective or unskillful communication. Invariably, we can attest that teaching is comparatively more difficult than to learn because effective teaching does not only depend upon the teachers' knowledge of the subject content, but mostly on how to use different methodologies and styles of communication skills. Secondly, it depends on the students' abilities, their interest, attitude, language, capabilities, and levels (age) of the learner. In as much as teaching doesn't only depend on teachers teaching capabilities alone, it also relates to students learning capabilities. Consequently, effective teachers' communication skills will effectively increase students' knowledge. Therefore, teachers' communication skills in the classroom have a very significant role in the academic success and behavioral development of the students. Noting the importance of effectiveness communication skills by the teachers in teaching-learning situation, it becomes very pertinent for teachers to be knowledgeable about effective communication skills in teaching the students. Finally, the need for continuous training for teachers to support their multifaceted work needs to be focused upon during teachers, pre-service, and the in-service training programmes.

Recommendations

Communication is essential to human existence, and all living creatures need to skillfully communicate in order to survive (Çelik & Alpan, 2022). It has been observed that empathy and communication training are necessary and also beneficial for almost every profession that communication plays a vital role, particularly in need are those working in many human-facing fields, such as the doctors, nurses, dentists, accountants, and engineers. (Cheraghi et al., 2021, and Moura et al., 2021). The researchers are happy that recently, the existing literature indicates that the number of studies focusing on teachers' competencies in communication skills have increased, and a large body of national and international researchers have been conducted to examine preservice teachers' communication skills and its effect in the classroom (Ateş & Sağar, 2022; Beyaz, 2022; Burak & Durak, 2021; Saunders & Mills, 1999). Communication is noted to be the most important factor in education as the classroom is a complex communication space as effective communication is very essential for teachers as the achievement of their objectives or goals are only possible through successful communication in the classroom (Gelişli, 2019). Knowledge or ideas are only shared with effective and skillful communication, and also enriched when appropriate and accurate messages are sent by the teachers and received the students. Tariq and Ullah (2024), and Rosalyn Sword (2020), revealed that for teachers to clearly present their ideas properly to students, they must excel in four modes of communication, which includes listening, speaking, reading, and writing. Finally, effective written and spoken communication skills should be organized on regular bases for both in-service and for pre-service teachers to cope with the classroom realities.

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